

The role of laccase in synthesis and degradation of humic substances

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Soil organic matter (SOM) is the largest reservoir of organic carbon in terrestrial ecosystems. Up to 80% of SOM is represented by alkali-extractable compounds, defined as humic substances (HS). The pathways of their formation and decomposition are not fully understood yet. It is believed that it is largely an oxidative catalytic process with extracellular microbial phenoloxidases and peroxidases playing an important role in transformation of phenolic compounds – aromatic constituents and precursors of HS. Free radicals produced during phenolic substrates oxidation undergo spontaneous coupling or initiate depolymerization reactions. However, occurrence of free radical reactions under soil conditions, their role in the formation and stabilization of SOM and biochemical stability of high molecular weight humic components are still under the discussion. Here we show the importance of free-radical reactions catalyzed by laccase in synthesis, stabilization and transformation of humic components of SOM.

Laccase (benzene diol: oxidoreductase, EC 1.10.3.2) is one of the most common phenoloxidases in soils. It is produced by fungi and bacteria and catalyzes oxidation of phenolic substrates and aromatic amines by molecular oxygen which is reduced to water. Depending on the difference of redox potentials of an enzyme and a substrate, laccase can catalyze condensation and/or depolymerization reactions thus playing bifunctional role in synthesis and degradation of SOM. It occurs as two-domain (2D) and three-domain (3D) proteins. The 2D laccases are known exclusively in bacteria and catalyze substrate oxidation at alkaline pH values (8-9), while 3D laccases occur in both fungi and bacteria and catalyze substrate oxidation at acidic-neutral pH values (4-7). Therefore, two forms of laccase complement each other over a wide pH range during transformation of phenolic substrates. We developed a method to disentangle the 3D and 2D laccase-like oxidative activities in soils [1] and show that activities of both forms of laccase are comparable in organic and inorganic soil horizons. The average laccase activity was 0.17 U g^{-1} , peaking up to 1.2 U g^{-1} in the litter soil horizons and decreasing with soil depth to $0.01\text{--}0.37 \text{ U g}^{-1}$. Using naturally occurring values of laccase activities we studied the role of 3D laccase in binding and stabilization of lignin-derived phenolic acids on mineral phases at low substrate concentrations. Laccase enhanced phenolics binding by 2-3 times thus playing important role in C_{org} stabilization. We show that at low concentrations of phenolic monomers (0.01 mM) and flow-through conditions oxidative coupling reactions result in formation of fulvic-like compounds. High molecular compounds are formed at high substrate concentrations ($>2 \text{ mM}$) and under static conditions but are unstable when not bound to mineral soil phases, being depolymerized by laccase to low molecular weight fractions. 2D laccases catalyze only polymerization reactions of humic components thus playing important role in molecular stabilization of SOM. Preservation and enhancement of the natural level of laccase activity in soils, the introduction of laccase preparations in immobilized form into soils may be a promising approach to enhance humification as well as sequestration potential of soils.

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References.

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